

New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Dual Domination

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1 SYNOPSIS

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
 & \quad \forall V_i \in V'', \exists V_j \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & \quad I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \quad \text{and} \\
 & \quad V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

In this scientific research, new configurations are introduced for the new SuperHyperNotions, namely a Strongly Stable Dual Domination and a Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination. Two different SuperHyperDefinitions were started for them, but research has progressed and SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass are well-defined and well-reviewed based on them. Literature review is implemented throughout this research. To shine the light and importance of this research, a comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and basic SuperHyperNumbers is presented. Definitions are followed by examples and examples, so clarifications are guided by various tools. Applications are designed to understand the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. “Cancer diagnosis” are the things that are being researched to explore the challenges that make sense in ongoing research and future research. It is a special case. Cells are viewed in the intended manner. There are different types of them. Some are individual and some are well modeled by groups of cells. All these types are officially called “SuperHyperVertex”, but the relationships between them all are officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” frameworks are selected and selected for research on “Cancer Diagnosis”. Thus, these complex and dense super-hypermodels open avenues for research on theoretical aspects and “cancer diagnosis”. Ways to pursue this scientific research have been considered. It has also

been formally collected in the form of several questions and problems. It is useful to define a “neutrosophic” version of Strongly Stable Dual Domination. Since there are more ways to get type results a Strongly Stable Dual Domination becomes more understandable. In order to master the Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “Strongly Stable Dual Domination mastery”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Suppose a Strongly Stable Dual Domination. If the specified table contains “values of vertices, supervertices, edges, hyperedges, and hyperedges belonging to Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with key points, it is redefined. ”values of vertices & number of positions in alphabet”, ”Values of SuperVertices&maximum values of its vertices”, ”values of edges&maximum values of its vertices”, ”super edge values&max values of its vertices”, “super edge values” and maximum values of its endpoints”. To get examples and structural examples, I would like to introduce the next SuperHyperClass SuperHyperGraph based on Strongly Stable Dual Domination. This is the original. Having the foundation of the previous definition in the SuperHyperClass type would be disciplined. If there is a need to have all Strongly Stable Dual Domination until Strongly Stable Dual Domination, then it is officially called “Strongly Stable Dual Domination”, but otherwise, it is not Strongly Stable Dual Domination. There is some explanation for the original definition titled “Strongly Stable Dual Domination”. These two examples are further explored and distinguished because they are characterized in the SuperHyperClass disciplinary methods based on a dominant Strongly Stable Dual Domination. Because of having Strongly Stable Dual Domination, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination” and “neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” is redefined if the desired table exists. And if the desired table exists, a Strongly Stable Dual Domination is redefined to a “Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination”. It is useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there are more ways to obtain Neutrosophic type results, a SuperHyper- Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination becomes more understandable. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If the desired table exists, there are a number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. So are SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite and SuperHyperWheel. ”Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel”. A graph is SuperHyperUniform if it is a SuperHyperGraph and the number of SuperHyperEdges elements is the same. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are a number of SuperHyperClasses as follows. It is a SuperHyperPath if there is only one SuperVertex as an intersection between two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions. If only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, it is SuperHyperCycle. It is SuperHyperStar and only one SuperVertex as intersection among all SuperHyperEdges. It is SuperHyperBipartite, and only one SuperVertex is given as the intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form two distinct sets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. This is SuperHyperMultiPartite. Only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form separate multisets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. If only one SuperHyperEdge among the given two SuperHyperEdges is a SuperHyperWheel and a SuperVertex has a SuperHyperEdge with any regular SuperVertex. SuperHyperModel suggests specific designs and specific architectures. SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel,

the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperVertices” and the common and desired properties between the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells. SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, to have a more accurate SuperHyperModel, it is useful to have some degree of determinism, uncertainty, and neutrality, in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In future scientific research, the foundation will be based on “diagnosis of cancer” and the results and definitions will be introduced in redeemed methods. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. There are some specific models, which are well known and have names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized with a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find the longest Strongly Stable Dual Domination or the strongest Strongly Stable Dual Domination in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are presented for the longest Strongly Stable Dual Domination called Strongly Stable Dual Domination and the strongest Strongly Stable Dual Domination called Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of any cycle, but literally, it is the transformation of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form. A basic introduction to the theory of Strongly Stable Dual Domination Neutrosophic, SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs is suggested.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are ideas in the prominent frameworks of motivations. I try to bring motivations in narrative ways. Some Cells have faced attacks from the established situation with cancer attacks in this case, there is some analysis embedded in the case current situations where cells can be labeled as some groups and some groups or individuals are overlabeled, all from behaviors to overcome cancer attacks. In embedded situations, cell individuals and cell groups can be considered as “new groups”. So it encourages us to find suitable SuperHyperModels for more appropriate analysis about this dirty story. I found SuperHyperModels, officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and relationships between individual cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. So this is another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on “cancer diagnosis”. Sometimes, things get worse. The situation has passed certainty and precise style. So it is beyond them. There are three descriptions, i.e., degrees of determination, uncertainty, and neutrality, for any object based on ambiguous forms, i.e., incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The second model can be considered in the previous

SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperGraph but officially called “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Cancer is a disease, but the model is supposed to understand what happens in this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and some parameters are used as consequences of the model. Cells are attacked by the disease, but the movement of cancer is in a specific area. Knowing the mind of cancer can help to find some cures for this disease. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic Super-HyperGraph are super-hypermodels used in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes based on the links of cancer movements in the form of unity styles with the formation of design and architecture officially called “Strongly Stable Dual Domination”, in the themes of specialized terms and common words. Particle for direct object. Applied concepts under the investigation of the motivation of this scientific research. The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the theme of embedded styles for background discovery for SuperHyperNotions. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of Cancer is not easy to identify because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of Cancer in that region. This event leads us to choose another model [said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph]. Easy understanding of what happened and what was done. There are some specific models that are well known and named and some general models. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a neutrosophic superhyperpath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find Strongly Stable Dual Domination or Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination for SuperHyperModels in it. Some general results are presented. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of cycle, but it is literally a form of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form.

Question 2.1. *How to define “SuperHyperNotions and to do research” to find the “Strongly Stable Dual Domination Rate” of any cell or groups of cells based on fixed cell or fixed group of cells broadly, “Strongly Stable Dual Domination Rate” based on fixed groups or fixed cells. Groups of groups of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for “diagnosing cancer” in terms of these chaotic and dense super-hypermodels in which embedded concepts are depicted?*

This motivation to find concepts to use in this dense model is called “SuperHyperGraphs”. So it motivates us to define different types of “Strongly Stable Dual Domination” and “neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination” over “superhypergraph” and “neutrosophic superhypergraph”. Then this scientific research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and find some connections among this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to obtain examples and examples to clarify the framework of this scientific research. The general results and some of the results about some of the connections are the ways that the key point of this scientific research, “diagnosis of cancer” is more understandable and clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. First, I will introduce the basic definitions to clarify the basics. In the “Introductions” subsection, basic definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are introduced and discussed in depth. Basic concepts are thoroughly explained and illustrated, and sometimes a literature review is used to make sense of what is to come in the coming

sections. The main definitions and their explanations, along with some results on the new concepts, Strongly Stable Dual Domination and Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination, are specified in the sections “Strongly Stable Dual Domination” and “Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination”. In the concept of dealing with results and in Strongly Stable Dual Domination to create logic about the continuation of the scientific research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, the corresponding SuperHyperClasses are specified to summarize the work done in this section, as “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. Going back to the core concepts, clever steps towards common concepts to extend new concepts in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” sections. There is the initial scientific research on supergeneral relations and as the final and final part of the theoretical scientific research is available in the section “General results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and are known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions, as in “General results” were extracted and discussed. “Strongly Stable Dual Domination”, “Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what has been done about SuperHyperNotions to make sense of the superiority of this scientific research and to discover the word “best” as a description and adjective of this scientific research as presented in the “Strongly Stable Dual Domination” section. The keyword of this scientific research was presented in the section “Applications in cancer diagnosis” with two cases and sub-sections “Case 1: Initial steps towards SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: Incremental steps towards SuperHyperMultiperdel as SuperHyper”. In the “open issues” section, there is a detailed examination and recognition of what was done in this scientific research and what happened in this scientific research in the form of “questions” and “issues” in order to understand this scientific research in an outstanding style, the advantages and limitations of this scientific research in addition to What has been done in this scientific research is stated in the “conclusion and final remarks” section.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [1]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [1]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a **Eulerian-Path-Cut** of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref.** [1], Definition 2.2, p.2).

Let X be a **Eulerian-Path-Cut** of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (**Ref.** [1], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

(ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Example 3.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.

- On the Figure (3), the SuperHyperNotion, namely, SuperHyperGirth, is up. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 .
- On the Figure (4), there's no empty SuperHyperEdge but E_3 are a loop SuperHyperEdge on $\{F\}$ and there are some SuperHyperEdges, namely, E_1 on $\{H, V_1, V_3\}$, alongside E_2 on $\{O, H, V_4, V_3\}$ and E_4, E_5 on $\{N, V_1, V_2, V_3, F\}$.
- On the Figure (5), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (6), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (7), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (8), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (9), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (10), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (11), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 4. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 5. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs mentioned as the SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 6. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 7. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs depicted SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 8. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with dense SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 9. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a messy SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 10. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-embedding-connected SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 11. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (12), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 300
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- On the Figure (13), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 302
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- On the Figure (14), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 304
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- On the Figure (15), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 306
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- On the Figure (16), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 308
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- On the Figure (17), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 310
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- On the Figure (18), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 312
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- On the Figure (19), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 314
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- On the Figure (20), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 316
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- On the Figure (21), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 318
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- On the Figure (22), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 320
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Figure 12. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-multiple-connected-style SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 13. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 14. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 15. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with Linearly-Connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 16. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 17. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a Linearly-over-packed SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 18. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 19. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 20. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 21. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 22. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Definition 3.7 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG).

Definition 3.8 (t-norm). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$;
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$;
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$;

(iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

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Definition 3.9. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.10. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.11. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

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Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

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(i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;

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(ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

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(iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;

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(iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

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(v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

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(vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

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(vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

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(viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

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Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

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Definition 3.12 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

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Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

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(i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;

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- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 377
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 378
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 379
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- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 381
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- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 383
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This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities. 385
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Definition 3.13. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. 388
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To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable. 390
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Definition 3.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. 392
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- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; 394
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- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; 396
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- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; 398
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- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 400
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- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 403
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- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. 406
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Example 3.15. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the notion. 409
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Example 3.16. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is up. 412
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Example 3.17. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is up. 415
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Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.15)

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.16)

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.17)

Example 3.18. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is up.

Example 3.19. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is up.

Example 3.20. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is up.

Definition 3.21. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_i$;

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.20)

- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 441
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 442
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 443
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 444
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 445
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 446
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 447
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 448
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Definition 3.22. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 450

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 451

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 452
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's V_i , $|V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 453
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 454
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| \geq 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**. 455
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Definition 3.23 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 457
(Ref. [1], Definition 5.3, p.7). 458

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$; 459
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$; 460
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$; 461
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$. 462

Definition 3.24 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.4, p.7). 463

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 464

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 465
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 466
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 467
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$. 468

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. 469

Definition 3.25. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds. 470

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable. 471

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.26)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Definition 3.26. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, notion, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite,** and **Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic notion. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic notion more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic notion". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.27. Assume a notion. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic notion** if the Table (3) holds.

Example 3.28. Referred to the Example (3.6), assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (4).

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.03, 0.03, 0.03)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 6. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
-	-	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (5). 512
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- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (6). 514
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- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (7). 516
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4 Main Resultant 518

Definition 4.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination). 519
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination criteria holds. 521
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))|
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 7. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)
V_3	(0.05, 0.05, 0.05)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.12, 0.12, 0.12)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{F\}$	(0.06, 0.06, 0.06)	E_5	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{H\}$	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)	-	-
$\{N\}$	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	-	-
$\{O\}$	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	-	-

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Table 8. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\forall V_i \in V'', \exists V_j \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)],$$

$$I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)],$$

$$F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)],$$

and

$$V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.|.$$

Example 4.2. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (8).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,5}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,5}} T(V_i),$$

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 31. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 32. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 33. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 34. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 35. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 36. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 37. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 38. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 39. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 40. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 41. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Table 9. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,5}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,5}} F(V_i) | \\
 & = (1.3, 1.3, 1.3) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 & \forall V_{i \neq 2,5} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,5}, \exists V_2 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=2,5} : \\
 & T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \text{and} \\
 & V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (9).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2,5}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2,5}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2,5}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2,5}} F(V_i)) | \\
 & = (0.96, 0.96, 0.96) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 & \forall V_{i=7} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2,5}, \exists V_1 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-2,5} : \\
 & T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \forall V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2,5}, \exists V_2 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-2,5} : \\
 & T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)],
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 10. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 \forall V_{i=4,6} \in V'' &= \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2,5}, \exists V_5 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-2,5} : \\
 T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 \text{and} \\
 V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' &\Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E^*_{NSHG}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (31), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (10). 539
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,5}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds. 541
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$$\begin{aligned}
 &| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,5}} T(V_i), \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,5}} I(V_i), \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,5}} F(V_i) \right) | \\
 &= (0.72, 0.72, 0.72) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) | \\
 &\quad \forall V_{i=7} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,5}, \exists V_1 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-3,5} : \\
 &\quad T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 &\quad I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 &\quad F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 &\quad \forall V_{i=4,6} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,5}, \exists V_5 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-3,5} : \\
 &\quad T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 &\quad I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 &\quad F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 &\quad \text{and} \\
 &\quad V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E^*_{NSHG} \\
 &\quad \text{and} \\
 &\quad V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E^*_{NSHG}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 11. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

Table 12. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

- On the Figure (33), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (11). 545
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,6}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds. 547
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,6}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,6}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,6}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.69, 0.69, 0.69) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
 & \forall V_{i=4-5,7} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3,6}, \exists V_5 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-3,6} : \\
 & T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \text{and} \\
 & V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (35), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (12). 551
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_i\}_{i=4}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and 553
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Table 13. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i=4}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i=4}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i=4}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 & \forall V_4 \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=4}, \\
 & \exists V_5 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 4} : \\
 & T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \text{and} \\
 & V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^*\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (37), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (13).

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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0, 0, 0) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 & \forall V_i \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7} = \{\}, \\
 & \exists V_j \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7} :
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 14. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 &\text{and} \\
 V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' &\Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (32), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (14).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i \neq 2}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2}} T(V_i), \\
 &\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2}} I(V_i), \\
 &\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2}} F(V_i))| \\
 &= (1.56, 1.56, 1.56) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 &\forall V_{i \neq 2} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2}, \\
 &\exists V_2 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=2} : \\
 &T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 &I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 &F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 &\text{and} \\
 &V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (34), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (15).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i \neq 1-2}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and

Table 15. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 16. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (1.3, 1.3, 1.3) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 & \forall V_{i \neq 1-2} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-2}, \\
 & \exists V_2 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-2} : \\
 & T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \text{and} \\
 & V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^*\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (36), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (16).

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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i \neq 1-3}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3}} F(V_i))|
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 17. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3}} F(V_i) | \\
 &= (1.04, 1.04, 1.04) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 & \quad \forall V_{i \neq 1-3} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-3}, \\
 & \quad \exists V_2 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-3} : \\
 & \quad T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & \quad I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \quad \text{and} \\
 & \quad V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (38), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (17).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-4}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-4}} T(V_i), \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-4}} I(V_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-4}} F(V_i) \right) | \\
 &= (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 & \quad \forall V_{i \neq 1-4} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-4}, \\
 & \quad \exists V_2 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-4} : \\
 & \quad T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & \quad I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \quad \text{and} \\
 & \quad V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 18. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 19. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

- On the Figure (39), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (18).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i \neq 1-5}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-5}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-5}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-5}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \forall V_{i \neq 1-5} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-5}, \\
 & \exists V_2 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-5} : \\
 & T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \text{and} \\
 & V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (40), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (19).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i \neq 1-6}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and

Table 20. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-6}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-6}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-6}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 & \forall V_{i \neq 1-6} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-6}, \\
 & \exists V_2 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-6} : \\
 & T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 & I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 & F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) = \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 & \text{and} \\
 & V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' \Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^*\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (41), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (20).

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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i \neq 1-7}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Dual Domination criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0, 0, 0) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 & \forall V_{i \neq 1-7} \in V'' = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7} = \{\}, \\
 & \exists V_2 \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' = \{V_i\}_{i=1-7} :
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[T_V(V_i), T_V(V_j)], \\
 I'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[I_V(V_i), I_V(V_j)], \\
 F'_V(E_{V_i, V_j}) &= \min[F_V(V_i), F_V(V_j)], \\
 &\text{and} \\
 V_a, V_b \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' &\Rightarrow V_a, V_b \notin E_{NSHG}^* \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

5 Main Result 607

Theorem 5.1. (Main Result and Main Theorem). 608

Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar has the letter z . The notion on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel coincides. 609
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Proof. 611

(i). Let 612

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 CENTER, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$
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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 614
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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. 616
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(ii). Let 619

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 CENTER, E_2^*
 \end{aligned}$$
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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2^*, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 621
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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.2. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.3. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination number is as follows.*

$$0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*,$$

$CENTER, E_2^*$

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$P :$
 $E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL},$
 $E_2^*, CENTER$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Proposition 5.4. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination set is as follows.*

$\{CENTER\}$.

Proof. Let

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$P :$
 $V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1,$
 $CENTER, E_2$

656

$P :$
 $E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL},$
 $E_2, CENTER$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Proposition 5.5. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination number is as follows.*

0.26.

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 5.6. (Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel**.

Proposition 5.7. Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination set is as follows.

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.8. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination number is lower than as follows.*

0.26.

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.9. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.10. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination number is lower than as follows.*

$$0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.11. *(Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel).*

(i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic CENTER has the letter maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination set.

(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic CENTER has the letter maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable

Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.12. (Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then $CENTER$ is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination set.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then $CENTER$ is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination set.

Proof.

- (i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward.

- (ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

6 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what’s going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it’s called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn’t be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it’s said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what’s happened and what’s done.

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they’ve got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

7 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (42), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic

Figure 43. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination

Table 22. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

SuperHyperModel (43), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination. 826

9 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition 827

Cancer is a neutrosophic disease, but the neutrosophic model is supposed to understand what is going on in this neutrosophic phenomenon. The special case of neutrosophic disease is considered and some parameters have been used as consequences of the model. Cells are subject to attack by the disease, but the movements of the cancer in the specific area is a matter of mind. Neutrosophic diagnosis of cancer can help in finding some Neutrosophic cures for this Neutrosophic disease. 828

In the following, several Neutrosophic stages are designed for this disease. 829

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) Neutrosophic diagnosis of cancer in long-term Neutrosophic performance. 830

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region is assigned by the Neutrosophic model (called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph) and the long Neutrosophic cycle of movement of cancer is identified by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. 831

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models that are well known and have names and some general Neutrosophic models. Cancer neutrosophic movements and effects in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find dominant neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination models or dominant sStrongly Stable Dual Domination models.

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?*

Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination?*

Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination?*

Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperStrongly Stable Dual Domination, are there else?*

Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 10.7. *What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, closing and concluding remarks are presented. The drawbacks of this scientific research are shown. Some advantages and disadvantages of this scientific research are highlighted.

This scientific research uses some approaches to further understand the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. In this effort, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the Strongly Stable Dual Domination. For this reason, in the second definition, the original definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph definition, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination, finds a suitable background to implement some results on. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the subjects of this scientific research on modeling areas that are subject to cancer attacks in order to recognize this disease as mentioned under the title “Cancer Diagnosis”. To formalize the SuperHyperNotion, Strongly Stable Dual Domination, SuperHyperClasses and new SuperHyperClasses instances are introduced. Some general results are summarized in the Strongly Stable Dual

Domination and Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination sections. Clarifications, examples, and literature reviews go all the way. In this scientific research, the literature review has met the lines containing concepts and results. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are super-hypermodels in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes SuperHyperNotions, formally called “Strongly Stable Dual Domination”, based on the connections of Cancer’s movements in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of design and architecture, in terms of terms and whispering words. . The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the topic of embedded styles to explore the background of SuperHyperNotions. In the table (23), the advantages and

Table 23. A look at this scientific research and beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. Strongly Stable Dual Domination	
3. Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Dual Domination	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. modeling cancer diagnoses	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

ways of this scientific research are specified, pointed out and expressed.

12 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this scientific research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms with introducing used neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Current Trends in Mass Communication (CTMC)*” with ISO abbreviation “*Curr Trends Mass Comm*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 32-55.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry

Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer's Recognition. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 3 with pages 136-148. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*" in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 6 with pages 221-307. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*" in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*" with ISO abbreviation "*IJPAMR*" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 60-88 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*" in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*" with ISO abbreviation "*IJPAMR*" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 102-124 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*" in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal

paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs*” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 16-24. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. In some articles are titled “*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph*” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs*” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*” in **Ref. [24]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With*

SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer's Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses in **Ref. [25]** by Henry Garrett (2022),
"SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer's Recognitions" in **Ref. [26]** by Henry Garrett (2022),
"Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer's Treatments" in **Ref. [27]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses"* in **Ref. [28]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer's Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [243]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer's Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [244]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer's Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer's Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [245]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer's Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer's Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [246]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [249]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer's Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique"* in **Ref. [250]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [253]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer's Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [256]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints"* in **Ref. [257]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer's Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [258]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond"* in **Ref. [259]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [260]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [261]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph"* in **Ref. [272]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)"* in **Ref. [273]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4-273], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph alongside scientific research books at [274-415]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [416, 417].

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [416]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google

Scholar and has more than 5679 readers in Scribd. It's titled "*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*" and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [417]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 6667 readers in Scribd. It's titled "*Neutrosophic Duality*" and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It's smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what's done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–273] alongside scientific research books at [274–415]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd, in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [416, 417].

References

1. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot", *Curr Trends Mass Comm* 2(1) (2023) 32-55. (doi: 10.33140/CTMC.02.01.03).
2. Henry Garrett, "*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer's Treatments*", *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.01.05).
3. Henry Garrett, "*A Research on Cancer's Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*", *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(3) (2023) 136-148. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.03.03).
4. Henry Garrett, "*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*", *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(6) (2023) 221-307. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.06.04).
5. Henry Garrett, "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*", *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 60-88. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88).
6. Henry Garrett, "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*", *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 102-124. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124).
7. Henry Garrett, "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*", *J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res* 2(1) (2023) 16-24. (doi: 10.33140/JCTCSR.02.01.04)

8. Henry Garrett, “*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09) 1132
1133
1134
1135
9. Garrett, Henry. “0039 — *Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. 1136
1137
1138
1139
1140
<https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942> 1141
10. Garrett, Henry. “0049 — *(Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. 1142
1143
1144
<https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724> 1145
<https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724> 1146
11. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1147
1148
1149
1150
12. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1151
1152
1153
1154
13. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 1155
1156
1157
14. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1158
1159
1160
1161
1162
1163
15. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1164
1165
1166
1167
16. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1168
1169
1170
1171
17. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1172
1173
1174
1175
18. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1176
1177
1178

19. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1).
1179
1180
1181
1182
20. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044
1183
1184
1185
21. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1).
1186
1187
1188
22. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1).
1189
1190
1191
1192
23. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1).
1193
1194
1195
1196
24. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1).
1197
1198
1199
25. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1).
1200
1201
1202
1203
1204
26. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1).
1205
1206
1207
27. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1).
1208
1209
1210
1211
28. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1).
1212
1213
1214
1215
29. Henry Garrett, “*Star and Wheel on Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph with a Specific Type of Independency of SuperHyperVertices*”, Preprints 2024, , 2024020663 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202402.0663.v1).
1216
1217
1218
1219
30. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Simple Dual Domination*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11253553).
1220
1221
1222

31. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11218489).
1223
1224
1225
32. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11169069).
1226
1227
1228
33. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11075522).
1229
1230
1231
34. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10982844).
1232
1233
1234
35. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10963312).
1235
1236
1237
36. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10929590).
1238
1239
1240
37. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10918770).
1241
1242
1243
38. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10910154).
1244
1245
1246
39. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10899659).
1247
1248
1249
40. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10895887).
1250
1251
1252
41. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10888691).
1253
1254
1255
42. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Star and Counteroffer Wheel By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10851065).
1256
1257
1258
1259
43. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Bipartite and Counteroffer Path By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10796076).
1260
1261
1262
1263
44. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Multipartite and Counteroffer Cycle By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10640905).
1264
1265
1266
1267

45. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17389.97769).
1268
1269
1270
1271
46. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28685.10727).
1272
1273
1274
1275
47. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24994.20169).
1276
1277
1278
1279
48. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10371529).
1280
1281
1282
49. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10299535).
1283
1284
1285
50. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10263440).
1286
1287
1288
1289
51. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10028600).
1290
1291
1292
52. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8310454).
1293
1294
1295
53. Henry Garrett, “Recognition of Cancer With Bipartite and Path as Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By the Tool Called Stability”, Preprints 2023, 2023081972 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202308.1972.v1).
1296
1297
1298
54. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8262182).
1299
1300
1301
55. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206877).
1302
1303
1304
1305
56. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206834).
1306
1307
1308
1309
57. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206773).
1310
1311
1312
1313

58. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201319). 1314
1315
1316
1317
59. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201255). 1318
1319
1320
1321
60. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201165). 1322
1323
1324
1325
61. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196147). 1326
1327
1328
1329
62. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196132). 1330
1331
1332
1333
63. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196099). 1334
1335
1336
1337
64. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8187955). 1338
1339
1340
65. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8161878). 1341
1342
1343
66. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8176262). 1344
1345
1346
67. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect Search As Hyper Perf On Super Perfidy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104836). 1347
1348
1349
68. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Perfidy By Hyper Perf Of SuperHyperPerfect Search In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104857). 1350
1351
1352
69. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092796). 1353
1354
1355
70. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092766). 1356
1357
1358

71. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088438). 1359
1360
1361
72. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Unequal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088387). 1362
1363
1364
73. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084436). 1365
1366
1367
74. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084420). 1368
1369
1370
75. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Connective As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080100). 1371
1372
1373
76. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Strict Connective In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080068). 1374
1375
1376
77. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078445). 1377
1378
1379
78. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Unequal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078543). 1380
1381
1382
79. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076416). 1383
1384
1385
80. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Strict Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076399). 1386
1387
1388
81. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072171). 1389
1390
1391
82. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072267). 1392
1393
1394
83. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067384). 1395
1396
1397
84. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Equal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067409). 1398
1399
1400
85. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8061927). 1401
1402
1403

86. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062016). 1404
1405
1406
87. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057696). 1407
1408
1409
88. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057753). 1410
1411
1412
89. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052893). 1413
1414
1415
90. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Equal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052925). 1416
1417
1418
91. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051346). 1419
1420
1421
92. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051360). 1422
1423
1424
93. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By United Dominating As Hyper Ultra On Super Units”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8025707). 1425
1426
1427
94. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Units By Hyper Ultra Of United Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027275). 1428
1429
1430
95. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Zero Forcing As Hyper ford On Super forceps”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8017246). 1431
1432
1433
96. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super forceps By Hyper ford Of Zero Forcing In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020128). 1434
1435
1436
97. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Matrix-Based As Hyper mat On Super matte”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978571). 1437
1438
1439
98. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super mat By Hyper matte Of Matrix-Based In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978857). 1440
1441
1442
99. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dominating-Edges As Hyper Dome On Super Eddy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7940830). 1443
1444
1445
100. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Dome Of Dominating-Edges In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943578). 1446
1447
1448

101. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Gap As Hyper Gape On Super Gab”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7916595). 1449
1450
1451
102. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gab By Hyper Gape Of Edge-Gap In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923632). 1452
1453
1454
103. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904698). 1455
1456
1457
104. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904671). 1458
1459
1460
105. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904529). 1461
1462
1463
1464
106. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904401). 1465
1466
1467
1468
107. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7871026). 1469
1470
1471
108. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874647). 1472
1473
1474
109. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857856). 1475
1476
1477
110. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857841). 1478
1479
1480
111. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855661). 1481
1482
1483
112. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855637). 1484
1485
1486
113. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853867). 1487
1488
1489
114. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853922). 1490
1491
1492

115. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851519). 1493
1494
1495
116. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851550). 1496
1497
1498
117. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7839333). 1499
1500
1501
118. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7840206). 1502
1503
1504
119. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834229). 1505
1506
1507
120. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834261). 1508
1509
1510
121. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824560). 1511
1512
1513
122. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824623). 1514
1515
1516
123. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819531). 1517
1518
1519
124. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819579). 1520
1521
1522
125. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812236). 1523
1524
1525
126. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By initial Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper initial Eulogy On Super initial EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809365). 1526
1527
1528
127. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut On Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809358). 1529
1530
1531
128. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809219). 1532
1533
1534
129. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809328). 1535
1536
1537

130. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806767). 1538
1539
1540
131. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806838). 1541
1542
1543
132. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804238). 1544
1545
1546
1547
133. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804228). 1548
1549
1550
134. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7799902). 1551
1552
1553
135. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804218). 1554
1555
1556
136. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7796334). 1557
1558
1559
137. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793372). 1560
1561
1562
138. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791952). 1563
1564
1565
139. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791982). 1566
1567
1568
140. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790026). 1569
1570
1571
141. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790052). 1572
1573
1574
142. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787066). 1575
1576
1577
143. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787094). 1578
1579
1580

144. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7781476). 1581
1582
1583
145. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783082). 1584
1585
1586
146. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7777857). 1587
1588
1589
147. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Trace-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7779286). 1590
1591
1592
148. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7771831). 1593
1594
1595
149. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Trace-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7772468). 1596
1597
1598
150. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20913.25446). 1599
1600
1601
151. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Tract By Hyper Track Of Trace-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7764916). 1602
1603
1604
152. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11770.98247). 1605
1606
1607
153. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Edge-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12400.12808). 1608
1609
1610
154. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22545.10089). 1611
1612
1613
155. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Edge-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29544.34564). 1614
1615
1616
156. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Cut As Hyper Edify On Super Eddy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11377.76644). 1617
1618
1619
157. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Edify Of Edge-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23750.96329). 1620
1621
1622
158. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31366.24641). 1623
1624
1625

159. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Vertex-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34721.68960). 1626
1627
1628
160. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30212.81289). 1629
1630
1631
161. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Vertex-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18468.76169). 1632
1633
1634
162. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Cut As Hyper Vertu On Super Vertigo*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24288.35842). 1635
1636
1637
163. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Vertigo By Hyper Vertu Of Vertex-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32467.25124). 1638
1639
1640
164. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31025.45925). 1641
1642
1643
165. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Stable-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17184.25602). 1644
1645
1646
166. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23423.28327). 1647
1648
1649
167. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28456.44805). 1650
1651
1652
168. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 1653
1654
1655
169. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 1656
1657
1658
170. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 1659
1660
1661
171. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 1662
1663
1664
172. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 1665
1666
1667
173. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 1668
1669
1670

174. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 1671
1672
1673
175. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 1674
1675
1676
176. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 1677
1678
1679
177. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 1680
1681
1682
178. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 1683
1684
1685
179. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 1686
1687
1688
180. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 1689
1690
1691
181. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 1692
1693
1694
182. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 1695
1696
1697
183. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 1698
1699
1700
184. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 1701
1702
1703
185. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 1704
1705
1706
186. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 1707
1708
1709
187. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 1710
1711
1712
188. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 1713
1714
1715

189. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 1716
1717
1718
190. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 1719
1720
1721
191. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 1722
1723
1724
192. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 1725
1726
1727
193. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 1728
1729
1730
194. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 1731
1732
1733
195. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 1734
1735
1736
196. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 1737
1738
1739
197. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 1740
1741
1742
198. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 1743
1744
1745
199. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 1746
1747
1748
200. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 1749
1750
1751
201. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 1752
1753
1754
202. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 1755
1756
1757
203. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 1758
1759
1760

204. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 1761
1762
1763
205. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 1764
1765
1766
206. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 1767
1768
1769
207. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 1770
1771
1772
208. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 1773
1774
1775
209. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 1776
1777
1778
210. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 1779
1780
1781
211. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 1782
1783
1784
212. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 1785
1786
1787
213. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 1788
1789
1790
214. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 1791
1792
1793
215. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 1794
1795
1796
216. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 1797
1798
1799
217. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 1800
1801
1802
218. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 1803
1804
1805

219. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 1806
1807
1808
220. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 1809
1810
1811
1812
221. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 1813
1814
1815
1816
222. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 1817
1818
1819
1820
223. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 1821
1822
1823
1824
224. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 1825
1826
1827
1828
225. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 1829
1830
1831
1832
226. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 1833
1834
1835
1836
227. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 1837
1838
1839
228. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 1840
1841
1842
229. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 1843
1844
1845
230. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 1846
1847
1848
1849

231. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 1850
1851
1852
1853
232. Henry Garrett, “*The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 1854
1855
1856
1857
1858
233. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 1859
1860
1861
1862
1863
234. Henry Garrett, “*Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 1864
1865
1866
1867
235. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 1868
1869
1870
236. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1871
1872
1873
1874
237. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1875
1876
1877
1878
238. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).). 1879
1880
1881
239. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1882
1883
1884
1885
1886
1887
240. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1888
1889
1890
1891
241. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1892
1893
1894
1895

242. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1896
1897
1898
1899
243. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 1900
1901
1902
244. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 1903
1904
1905
1906
245. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 1907
1908
1909
1910
246. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 1911
1912
1913
1914
247. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 1915
1916
1917
1918
248. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1919
1920
1921
249. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 1922
1923
1924
250. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 1925
1926
1927
1928
251. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1929
1930
1931
1932
252. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1933
1934
1935
1936
253. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 1937
1938
1939
1940

254. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 1941
1942
1943
255. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 1944
1945
1946
256. Henry Garrett, “*Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 1947
1948
1949
257. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 1950
1951
1952
258. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 1953
1954
1955
259. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 1956
1957
1958
1959
260. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 1960
1961
1962
261. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 1963
1964
1965
1966
262. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 1967
1968
1969
263. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 1970
1971
1972
264. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 1973
1974
1975
1976
1977
265. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 1978
1979
1980
1981
1982
266. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 1983
1984
1985

267. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 1986
1987
1988
268. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 1989
1990
1991
1992
269. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 1993
1994
1995
1996
270. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 1997
1998
1999
2000
271. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 2001
2002
2003
2004
272. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 2005
2006
2007
273. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 2008
2009
2010
2011
274. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 1”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11106891). 2012
2013
275. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10946745). 2014
2015
276. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10909931). 2016
2017
277. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10871136). 2018
2019
278. Henry Garrett, “Stable Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10523307). 2020
2021
279. Henry Garrett, “Resolving Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10395711). 2022
2023
280. Henry Garrett, “Dominating Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10042973). 2024
2025
281. Henry Garrett, “Stable In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8210033). 2026
2027
282. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206898). 2028
2029

283. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201378). 2030
2031
284. Henry Garrett, “Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8194003). 2032
2033
285. Henry Garrett, “Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8113416). 2034
2035
286. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperPerfect Search In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104880). 2036
2037
287. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092816). 2038
2039
288. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8090194). 2040
2041
289. Henry Garrett, “Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8086310). 2042
2043
290. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Connective In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080167). 2044
2045
291. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078574). 2046
2047
292. Henry Garrett, “Strict Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076449). 2048
2049
293. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072310). 2050
2051
294. Henry Garrett, “Equal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067469). 2052
2053
295. Henry Garrett, “Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062076). 2054
2055
296. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057817). 2056
2057
297. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052976). 2058
2059
298. Henry Garrett, “Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051368). 2060
2061
299. Henry Garrett, “United Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027488). 2062
2063
300. Henry Garrett, “Zero Forcing In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020181). 2064
2065
301. Henry Garrett, “Matrix-Based In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978921). 2066
2067
302. Henry Garrett, “Collections of Math II”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943878). 2068
2069

303. Henry Garrett, “Dominating-Edges In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943871). 2070
2071
304. Henry Garrett, “Edge-Gap In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923786). 2072
2073
305. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7905287). 2074
2075
306. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904586). 2076
2077
307. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874677). 2078
2079
308. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857906). 2080
2081
309. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7856329). 2082
2083
310. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7854561). 2084
2085
311. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851893). 2086
2087
312. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7848019). 2088
2089
313. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7835063). 2090
2091
314. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7826705). 2092
2093
315. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7820680). 2094
2095
316. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812750). 2096
2097
317. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812142). 2098
2099
318. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7810394). 2100
2101
319. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7807782). 2102
2103
320. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804449). 2104
2105
321. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793875). 2106
2107
322. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7792307). 2108
2109

323. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790728). 2110
2111
324. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787712). 2112
2113
325. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783791). 2114
2115
326. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7780123). 2116
2117
327. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7773119). 2118
2119
328. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDuality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7637762). 2120
2121
329. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7766174). 2122
2123
330. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7762232). 2124
2125
331. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7758601). 2126
2127
332. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7754661). 2128
2129
333. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7750995) . 2130
2131
334. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7749875). 2132
2133
335. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7747236). 2134
2135
336. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7742587). 2136
2137
337. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7738635). 2138
2139
338. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7734719). 2140
2141
339. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Neighbors In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730484). 2142
2143
340. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730469). 2144
2145
341. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7722865). 2146
2147
342. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7713563). 2148
2149

343. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7709116). 2150
2151
344. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706415). 2152
2153
345. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706063). 2154
2155
346. Henry Garrett, “*Tree-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7701906). 2156
2157
347. Henry Garrett, “*Chord In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7700205). 2158
2159
348. Henry Garrett, “*(i,j)-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7694876). 2160
2161
349. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7679410). 2162
2163
350. Henry Garrett, “*K-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7675982). 2164
2165
351. Henry Garrett, “*K-Number In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7672388). 2166
2167
352. Henry Garrett, “*Order In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7668648). 2168
2169
353. Henry Garrett, “*Coloring In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7662810). 2170
2171
354. Henry Garrett, “*Dimension In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7659162). 2172
2173
355. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653233). 2174
2175
356. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperWheel*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653204). 2176
2177
357. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMultipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653142). 2178
2179
358. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperBipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653117). 2180
2181
359. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStar*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653089). 2182
2183
360. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651687). 2184
2185
361. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPath*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651619). 2186
2187
362. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDomination*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651439). 2188
2189

363. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7650729). 2190
2191
364. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnected*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647868). 2192
2193
365. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperTotal*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647017). 2194
2195
366. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPerfect*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7644894). 2196
2197
367. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperJoin*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7641880). 2198
2199
368. Henry Garrett, “*Path SuperHyperColoring*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7632923). 2200
2201
369. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDensity*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7623459). 2202
2203
370. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2204
2205
371. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2206
2207
372. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606404). 2208
2209
373. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2210
2211
374. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2212
2213
375. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2214
2215
376. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7579929). 2216
2217
377. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563170). 2218
2219
378. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563164). 2220
2221
379. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2222
2223
380. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2224
2225
381. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2226
2227
382. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557063). 2228
2229

383. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557009). 2230
2231
384. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2232
2233
385. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2234
2235
386. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2236
2237
387. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2238
2239
388. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574952). 2240
2241
389. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574992). 2242
2243
390. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2244
2245
391. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2246
2247
392. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2248
2249
393. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2250
2251
394. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2252
2253
395. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2254
2255
396. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2256
2257
397. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2258
2259
398. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2260
2261
399. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2262
2263
400. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2264
2265
401. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2266
2267
402. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2268
2269

403. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2270
2271
404. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2272
2273
405. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2274
2275
406. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2276
2277
407. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2278
2279
408. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2280
2281
409. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2282
2283
410. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2284
2285
411. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2286
2287
412. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2288
2289
413. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2290
2291
414. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7480110). 2292
2293
415. Henry Garrett, “*Neut. SuperHyperEdges*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7378758). 2294
2295
416. Henry Garrett, “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6320305). 2296
2297
417. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Duality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6677173). 2298
2299